

Interoperable nanosafety data using semantic modeling and linked data knowledge graphs

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Supplementary File 2

Table S4. Results of a federated SPARQL query integrating NanoLinks-KG nanomaterial types with adverse outcomes from AOP-Wiki.

Material Type	Adverse Outcome Title	Key Event Count
npo:NPO_1373	Bronchiolitis obliterans	1
npo:NPO_1373	N/A, Breast Cancer	1
npo:NPO_1373	Decrease, Lung function	1
npo:NPO_1373	Atherosclerosis	1
npo:NPO_1373	Pulmonary fibrosis	2
npo:NPO_1373	Inflammatory events in light-exposed tissues	3
npo:NPO_1373	Oxidative Stress	3
npo:NPO_1373	Decreased sperm quantity or quality in the adult, Decreased fertility	3
npo:NPO_1373	Malformation, cryptorchidism - maldescended testis	3
npo:NPO_1373	Increased, mesotheliomas	3
npo:NPO_1373	N/A, Steatohepatitis	3
npo:NPO_1373	Chronic kidney disease	3
npo:NPO_1373	Insulin resistance, increased	3

npo:NPO_1373	anogenital distance (AGD), decreased	3
npo:NPO_1373	Apoptotic cell death	3
npo:NPO_1373	Cholestasis, Pathology	3
npo:NPO_1373	Increase, Vascular disrupting effects	3
npo:NPO_1373	Impairment, Learning and memory	3
npo:NPO_1373	Decreased, Viable Offspring	3
npo:NPO_1373	impaired, Fertility	3
npo:NPO_1373	Reproductive failure	3
npo:NPO_1373	Cognitive function, decreased	3
npo:NPO_1373	Metabolic syndrome	3
npo:NPO_1373	Treatment-resistant gastric cancer	4
npo:NPO_1373	Increased incidence of respiratory disease	5
npo:NPO_1373	Dysfunction of respiratory system	5
npo:NPO_1373	Lung fibrosis	6
npo:NPO_1373	Increased Mortality	6
npo:NPO_1373	Decrease, Fecundity	6
npo:NPO_1373	Decreased, Population size	6
npo:NPO_1373	N/A, Liver fibrosis	6
npo:NPO_1373	Decrease of egg production and cumulative fecundity	6

npo:NPO_1373	Reduction, Cumulative fecundity and spawning	6
npo:NPO_1373	Increase, Cancer	9
npo:NPO_1373	Lung cancer	10
npo:NPO_1373	Increase, Mortality	12
npo:NPO_1373	Decrease, Reproduction	15
npo:NPO_1373	Decrease, Population growth rate	21
npo:NPO_1542	Cholestasis, Pathology	3
npo:NPO_1542	Treatment-resistant gastric cancer	3
npo:NPO_1542	Apoptotic cell death	3
npo:NPO_1542	Insulin resistance, increased	3
npo:NPO_1542	Metabolic syndrome	3
npo:NPO_1542	Dysfunction of respiratory system	3
npo:NPO_1542	Increase, Vascular disrupting effects	3
npo:NPO_1542	Reproductive failure	3
npo:NPO_1542	Impairment, Learning and memory	3
npo:NPO_1542	Increased incidence of respiratory disease	3
npo:NPO_1542	Malformation, cryptorchidism - maldescended testis	3
npo:NPO_1542	Chronic kidney disease	3
npo:NPO_1542	N/A, Steatohepatitis	3

np0:NPO_1542	anogenital distance (AGD), decreased	3
np0:NPO_1542	Cognitive function, decreased	3
np0:NPO_1542	Decreased, Viable Offspring	3
np0:NPO_1542	Decreased sperm quantity or quality in the adult, Decreased fertility	3
np0:NPO_1542	Oxidative Stress	3
np0:NPO_1542	Inflamatory events in light-exposed tissues	3
np0:NPO_1542	Increased, mesotheliomas	3
np0:NPO_1542	impaired, Fertility	3
np0:NPO_1542	Increased, Liver Steatosis	3
np0:NPO_1542	N/A, Liver fibrosis	6
np0:NPO_1542	Increased Mortality	6
np0:NPO_1542	Decrease, Fecundity	6
np0:NPO_1542	Lung fibrosis	6
np0:NPO_1542	Decreased, Population size	6
np0:NPO_1542	Decrease of egg production and cumulative fecundity	6
np0:NPO_1542	Reduction, Cumulative fecundity and spawning	6
np0:NPO_1542	Increase, Cancer	9
np0:NPO_1542	Lung cancer	9
np0:NPO_1542	Increase, Mortality	12

npo:NPO_1542	Decrease, Reproduction	15
npo:NPO_1542	Decrease, Population growth rate	21
npo:NPO_1548	Decreased sperm quantity or quality in the adult, Decreased fertility	3
npo:NPO_1548	Oxidative Stress	3
npo:NPO_1548	Chronic kidney disease	3
npo:NPO_1548	Cognitive function, decreased	3
npo:NPO_1548	Increase, Vascular disrupting effects	3
npo:NPO_1548	Apoptotic cell death	3
npo:NPO_1548	Cholestasis, Pathology	3
npo:NPO_1548	Increased, mesotheliomas	3
npo:NPO_1548	Reproductive failure	3
npo:NPO_1548	impaired, Fertility	3
npo:NPO_1548	Malformation, cryptorchidism - maldescended testis	3
npo:NPO_1548	anogenital distance (AGD), decreased	3
npo:NPO_1548	Increased incidence of respiratory disease	3
npo:NPO_1548	N/A, Steatohepatitis	3
npo:NPO_1548	Inflamatory events in light-exposed tissues	3
npo:NPO_1548	Increased, Liver Steatosis	3
npo:NPO_1548	Dysfunction of respiratory system	3

npo:NPO_1548	Insulin resistance, increased	3
npo:NPO_1548	Decreased, Viable Offspring	3
npo:NPO_1548	Treatment-resistant gastric cancer	3
npo:NPO_1548	Impairment, Learning and memory	3
npo:NPO_1548	Metabolic syndrome	3
npo:NPO_1548	N/A, Liver fibrosis	6
npo:NPO_1548	Decrease of egg production and cumulative fecundity	6
npo:NPO_1548	Decrease, Fecundity	6
npo:NPO_1548	Decreased, Population size	6
npo:NPO_1548	Reduction, Cumulative fecundity and spawning	6
npo:NPO_1548	Lung fibrosis	6
npo:NPO_1548	Increased Mortality	6
npo:NPO_1548	Increase, Cancer	9
npo:NPO_1548	Lung cancer	9
npo:NPO_1548	Increase, Mortality	12
npo:NPO_1548	Decrease, Reproduction	15
npo:NPO_1548	Decrease, Population growth rate	21
npo:NPO_1550	Increased, Liver Steatosis	3
npo:NPO_1892	Increased, Kidney Failure	1

np0:NPO_1892	Decrease Left Ventricular function	1
np0:NPO_1892	Hyperinflammation	1
np0:NPO_1892	Occurrence, Bone Loss	1
np0:NPO_1892	Occurrence of Cataracts	1
np0:NPO_1892	Increase, Chromosomal aberrations	1
np0:NPO_1892	Facial cartilage structures are reduced in size and morphologically distorted	1
np0:NPO_1892	Intestinal barrier, disruption	1
np0:NPO_1892	decreased, Intellectual Quotient	1
np0:NPO_1892	Infant leukaemia	1
np0:NPO_1892	Apoptosis	1
np0:NPO_1892	Increase, DNA damage	1
np0:NPO_1892	Occurrence, Abnormal Vascular Remodeling	1
np0:NPO_1892	Neurodegeneration	1
np0:NPO_1892	Necrosis	1
np0:NPO_1892	Immune mediated hepatitis	1
np0:NPO_1892	Decrease, Lung function	1
np0:NPO_1892	Increase, lung cancer	1
np0:NPO_1892	Acute Myeloid Leukemia	1
np0:NPO_1892	Increase, Site of Contact Nasal Tumors	1

npo:NPO_1892	Decreased, Population trajectory	1
npo:NPO_1892	Increased, Disease susceptibility	1
npo:NPO_1892	Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease	1
npo:NPO_1892	Parkinsonian motor deficits	1
npo:NPO_1892	Reduce, Sperm count	2
npo:NPO_1892	Increase risk, microcephaly	2
npo:NPO_1892	Multi Organ Failure involving Acute Respiratory Distress Syndrome	2
npo:NPO_1892	N/A, Neurodegeneration	2
npo:NPO_1892	Necrotic Tissue	2
npo:NPO_1892	Increased, Ductal Hyperplasia	2
npo:NPO_1892	metastatic breast cancer	2
npo:NPO_1892	Treatment-resistant gastric cancer	3
npo:NPO_1892	Insulin resistance, increased	3
npo:NPO_1892	Cholestasis, Pathology	3
npo:NPO_1892	Orofacial clefting	3
npo:NPO_1892	Oxidative Stress	3
npo:NPO_1892	impaired, Fertility	3
npo:NPO_1892	Dysfunction of respiratory system	3
npo:NPO_1892	Metabolic syndrome	3

npo:NPO_1892	N/A, Breast Cancer	3
npo:NPO_1892	Liver Injury	3
npo:NPO_1892	Chronic kidney disease	3
npo:NPO_1892	Decreased, Viable Offspring	3
npo:NPO_1892	Cognitive function, decreased	3
npo:NPO_1892	Testicular atrophy	3
npo:NPO_1892	Neural tube defects	3
npo:NPO_1892	Increased incidence of respiratory disease	3
npo:NPO_1892	Inflammatory events in light-exposed tissues	3
npo:NPO_1892	N/A, Steatohepatitis	3
npo:NPO_1892	Increase, Mutations	3
npo:NPO_1892	Increase, Vascular disrupting effects	4
npo:NPO_1892	Reproductive failure	4
npo:NPO_1892	Increased, mesotheliomas	4
npo:NPO_1892	Decreased sperm quantity or quality in the adult, Decreased fertility	5
npo:NPO_1892	Apoptotic cell death	5
npo:NPO_1892	Malformation, cryptorchidism - maldescended testis	5
npo:NPO_1892	anogenital distance (AGD), decreased	5
npo:NPO_1892	Lung fibrosis	6

np0:NPO_1892	Decrease, Growth	6
np0:NPO_1892	Decrease of egg production and cumulative fecundity	7
np0:NPO_1892	Decreased, Population size	7
np0:NPO_1892	Reduction, Cumulative fecundity and spawning	8
np0:NPO_1892	N/A, Liver fibrosis	9
np0:NPO_1892	Increased Mortality	9
np0:NPO_1892	Impairment, Learning and memory	11
np0:NPO_1892	Increase, Cancer	11
np0:NPO_1892	Decrease, Fecundity (F3)	12
np0:NPO_1892	Lung cancer	13
np0:NPO_1892	Increase, Mortality	16
np0:NPO_1892	Decrease, Fecundity	19
np0:NPO_1892	Decrease, Reproduction	21
np0:NPO_1892	Decrease, Population growth rate	54
np0:NPO_354	Occurrence, Bone Loss	3
np0:NPO_354	Immune mediated hepatitis	3
np0:NPO_354	Reduce, Sperm count	3
np0:NPO_354	Decreased sperm quantity or quality in the adult, Decreased fertility	3
np0:NPO_354	Increased, Kidney Failure	3

npo:NPO_354	Increase, Allergic Respiratory Hypersensitivity Response	3
npo:NPO_354	Apoptosis	3
npo:NPO_354	metastatic breast cancer	3
npo:NPO_354	Reproductive failure	3
npo:NPO_354	Increase, Vascular disrupting effects	3
npo:NPO_354	Parkinsonian motor deficits	3
npo:NPO_354	Decrease, Lung function	3
npo:NPO_354	Increase risk, microcephaly	3
npo:NPO_354	decreased, Intellectual Quotient	3
npo:NPO_354	Decrease Left Ventricular function	3
npo:NPO_354	anogenital distance (AGD), decreased	3
npo:NPO_354	Testicular Cancer	3
npo:NPO_354	Necrosis	3
npo:NPO_354	Neurodegeneration	3
npo:NPO_354	Treatment-resistant gastric cancer	3
npo:NPO_354	Liver Cancer	3
npo:NPO_354	Testicular atrophy	3
npo:NPO_354	Intestinal barrier, disruption	3
npo:NPO_354	Malformation, cryptorchidism - maldescended testis	3

npo:NPO_354	Apoptotic cell death	3
npo:NPO_354	Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease	3
npo:NPO_354	Pulmonary fibrosis	5
npo:NPO_354	Atherosclerosis	5
npo:NPO_354	Decrease, Fecundity	6
npo:NPO_354	Prostate cancer	6
npo:NPO_354	Occurrence of Cataracts	6
npo:NPO_354	N/A, Neurodegeneration	6
npo:NPO_354	Formation, Hepatocellular and Bile duct tumors	6
npo:NPO_354	Lung fibrosis	6
npo:NPO_354	Decrease, Reproduction	6
npo:NPO_354	Increase, Mortality	6
npo:NPO_354	Increase, lung cancer	9
npo:NPO_354	Hyperinflammation	9
npo:NPO_354	Orofacial clefting	9
npo:NPO_354	Increase, Site of Contact Nasal Tumors	9
npo:NPO_354	Necrotic Tissue	9
npo:NPO_354	Increased, mesotheliomas	9
npo:NPO_354	Occurrence, Abnormal Vascular Remodeling	10

npo:NPO_354	Thromboinflammation, Increased	10
npo:NPO_354	Cholestasis, Pathology	10
npo:NPO_354	Liver Injury	12
npo:NPO_354	Acute Myeloid Leukemia	16
npo:NPO_354	Increase, DNA damage	16
npo:NPO_354	Decrease, Population growth rate	18
npo:NPO_354	Decrease, Growth	18
npo:NPO_354	Increase, Cancer	24
npo:NPO_354	Multi Organ Failure involving Acute Respiratory Distress Syndrome	29
npo:NPO_354	Increase, Mutations	32
npo:NPO_354	N/A, Liver fibrosis	32
npo:NPO_354	Increased, Ductal Hyperplasia	32
npo:NPO_354	N/A, Breast Cancer	35
npo:NPO_354	Increased Mortality	35
npo:NPO_354	Impairment, Learning and memory	37
npo:NPO_354	Lung cancer	39
npo:NPO_943	sensitisation, skin	1
npo:NPO_943	Increase, Allergic Respiratory Hypersensitivity Response	1
npo:NPO_943	Formation, Liver fibrosis	18

npo:NPO_943	Intestinal barrier, disruption	18
npo:NPO_943	N/A, Liver fibrosis	18
npo:NPO_943	Occurrence, Kidney toxicity	36
enm:ENM_9000006	Increase, lung cancer	3
enm:ENM_9000006	Increase, DNA damage	3
enm:ENM_9000006	Acute Myeloid Leukemia	3
enm:ENM_9000006	Increase risk, microcephaly	3
enm:ENM_9000006	metastatic breast cancer	3
enm:ENM_9000006	Infant leukaemia	3
enm:ENM_9000006	Reduce, Sperm count	3
enm:ENM_9000006	Increased, Liver Steatosis	3
enm:ENM_9000006	Decreased, Population trajectory	3
enm:ENM_9000006	Occurrence, Abnormal Vascular Remodeling	3
enm:ENM_9000006	Occurrence of Cataracts	3
enm:ENM_9000006	Increase, Chromosomal aberrations	3
enm:ENM_9000006	Increased, Ductal Hyperplasia	6
enm:ENM_9000006	Metabolic syndrome	9
enm:ENM_9000006	Reproductive failure	9
enm:ENM_9000006	Increase, Mutations	9

enm:ENM_9000006	N/A, Breast Cancer	9
enm:ENM_9000006	Treatment-resistant gastric cancer	9
enm:ENM_9000006	Increased incidence of respiratory disease	9
enm:ENM_9000006	Oxidative Stress	9
enm:ENM_9000006	Dysfunction of respiratory system	9
enm:ENM_9000006	impaired, Fertility	9
enm:ENM_9000006	Cholestasis, Pathology	9
enm:ENM_9000006	Insulin resistance, increased	9
enm:ENM_9000006	Inflammatory events in light-exposed tissues	9
enm:ENM_9000006	Increase, Vascular disrupting effects	9
enm:ENM_9000006	N/A, Steatohepatitis	9
enm:ENM_9000006	Chronic kidney disease	9
enm:ENM_9000006	Cognitive function, decreased	9
enm:ENM_9000006	Decreased, Viable Offspring	9
enm:ENM_9000006	Impairment, Learning and memory	12
enm:ENM_9000006	anogenital distance (AGD), decreased	12
enm:ENM_9000006	Malformation, cryptorchidism - maldescended testis	12
enm:ENM_9000006	Decreased sperm quantity or quality in the adult, Decreased fertility	12
enm:ENM_9000006	Apoptotic cell death	12

enm:ENM_9000006	Increased, mesotheliomas	12
enm:ENM_9000006	Increased Mortality	18
enm:ENM_9000006	Lung fibrosis	18
enm:ENM_9000006	N/A, Liver fibrosis	18
enm:ENM_9000006	Decrease of egg production and cumulative fecundity	21
enm:ENM_9000006	Decreased, Population size	21
enm:ENM_9000006	Decrease, Fecundity	24
enm:ENM_9000006	Reduction, Cumulative fecundity and spawning	24
enm:ENM_9000006	Increase, Cancer	27
enm:ENM_9000006	Lung cancer	39
enm:ENM_9000006	Increase, Mortality	42
enm:ENM_9000006	Decrease, Reproduction	57
enm:ENM_9000006	Decrease, Population growth rate	81
obo:CHEBI_33416	sensitisation, skin	1
obo:CHEBI_33416	Increase, Allergic Respiratory Hypersensitivity Response	1